

CODEN [USA]: IAJPB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**THE KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE, AND PRACTICES
RELATING TO TUBERCULOSIS AMONG
DRUG-RESISTANT TUBERCULOSIS PATIENTS**¹Dr.Khursheed Alam, ²Dr.Talha Bin Liaquat, ³Dr.Adnan khadim¹Quaid-e-Azam Medical College Bahawalpur, University of Health Sciences Lahore.**Article Received:** March 2020**Accepted:** April 2020**Published:** May 2020**Abstract:**

Background- Before diagnosis of tuberculosis in a patients and initiation of treatment, the infected person can infect some healthy people. In order to prevent the tuberculosis undiscerning spitting is like a challenge, as there is very limited awareness about tuberculosis.

Material and Methods- This is a cross sectional study carried out in Bahawalpur Victoria Hospital to evaluate the practices, attitude and knowledge about the tuberculosis by asking the questions with the help of semi-structured questionnaire to the patients of extensively drug-resistant tuberculosis and multidrug-resistant tuberculosis. In this we focused on the etiology, spreading mode, factor related to the treatment, attitude and treatment practices, and knowledge and attitude toward the prevention of spread such as sputum disposal.

Results: For this study we selected 250 patients including 135 females and 165 males having the mean age 29 ± 11 years. 241 of the patients had the correct knowledge about tuberculosis symptoms with the percentage of 96%, 235 had the correct knowledge about spreading mode i.e. 94%, 246 i.e. 98% know correct duration of treatment. All the patients have correct attitude toward anti-tubercular treatment. 246 patients know how to cover their mouth while sneezing and coughing. Additionally, only 18% i.e. 45 know about the correct disposal of sputum as 26% patients dispose off their sputum in open.

Conclusion- It was concluded during this study that despite of correct knowledge and attitude toward tuberculosis only a few ones are practically disposed of their sputum safely. There is a big gap in awareness about the correct disposal of sputum in people.

Keywords: Tuberculosis, practice, knowledge, attitude

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Please cite this article in press Khursheed Alam et al, *The Knowledge, Attitude, And Practices Relating To Tuberculosis Among Drug-Resistant Tuberculosis Patients.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(05).

INTRODUCTION:

Drug-resistant tuberculosis is an emerging problem globally. Before diagnosis of tuberculosis in a patients and initiation of treatment, the infected person can infect some healthy people. In order to prevent the tuberculosis undiscerning spitting is like a challenge, as there is very limited awareness about tuberculosis. The spread of tuberculosis can be prevented by simply practicing the practice like safe disposal of sputum and covering mouth while sneezing and coughing. By safely disposing of the saliva the spread of tuberculosis can be reduced to much extent. There is a big gap in awareness about the correct disposal of sputum in people, there should be special focus on health education so that people can be educated by recommended the simple prevention. In order to tuberculosis control program this study provide a valuable knowledge in prevention of tuberculosis. Excessive spitting in open environment is definitely a challenge in the prevention of tuberculosis. So we conducted this study in order to evaluate the knowledge, attitude and practice of tuberculosis patients.

METHODOLOGY:

This is a cross sectional study carried out in bahawalpur Victoria to evaluate the practices, attitude and knowledge about the tuberculosis by asking the questions with the help of semi-structured questionnaire to the patients of extensively drug-resistant tuberculosis and multidrug-resistant tuberculosis. In this we focused on the etiology, spreading mode, factor related to the treatment, attitude and treatment practices, and knowledge and attitude toward the prevention of spread such as sputum disposal. Each question in questionnaire had three answers “don’t know”,

DISCUSSION:

This study was done to assess the knowledge, attitude and practices of patients relating tuberculosis and toward its preventions.

“important”, “very important” and on the basis of answer the attitude of respondent was observed. In this study the definition of safe disposal of sputum was that spitting in bactericidal container or pouring boiled water in the spitting container whereas the unsafe disposal practices of sputum was defined as the spitting in public dustbin, spitting in open, indiscriminate spitting.

Analysis of Data:

The obtained data was entered in MS excel and for statistical analysis of data SPSS 22.0 was used in which results were expressed as standard deviation, mean, proportion, and frequency.

RESULTS:

For this study we selected 250 patients including 135 females and 165 males having the mean age 29 ± 11 years. 241 of the patients had the correct knowledge about tuberculosis symptoms with the percentage of 96%, 235 had the correct knowledge about spreading mode i.e. 94%, 246 i.e. 98% know correct duration of treatment. All the patients have correct attitude toward anti-tubercular treatment. 246 patients know how to cover their mouth while sneezing and coughing.

Additionally, only 18% i.e. 45 know about the correct disposal of sputum as 26% patients dispose of their sputum in open. 97% cover their mouth while sneezing and coughing. 92 patients i.e. 37% spit in open environment, 34% of them use spit container, 26% used public dustbin, 29% used wash bin for spitting. Whereas 7% didn’t care at all while spitting. 7.2% take care to keep away from children while spitting.

Table 1: Knowledge of etiology, spread, and treatment of tuberculosis among patients with drug-resistant tuberculosis (n=250)

TB germ	157
Don't know	(63)
Symptoms of	
TB Fever	241
Cough >2	(96)
weeks Loss	241
of appetite	(96)
Weight loss	
Mode of spread	232
Close contact through cough or	(93)

sneezing Dusty air	246
Treatment factors	
Correct knowledge on duration of treatment	227
Whether TB is curable	(91)
Yes	
No/don't know	248
(99)	
Factors related to cure of TB	141
Complete	

Figure 1: Common practices for prevention of spread of tuberculosis among drug resistant-tuberculosis patients

In order to prevent the tuberculosis undiscerning spitting is like a challenge, as there is very limited awareness about tuberculosis. The spread of tuberculosis can be prevented by simply practicing the practice like safe disposal of sputum and covering mouth while sneezing and coughing. By safely disposing the saliva the spread of tuberculosis can be reduced to much extent. There is a big gap in awareness about the correct disposal of sputum in people, there should be special focus on health education so that people can be educated by recommended the simple prevention. Practically all the patients in our examination knew that tuberculosis can be spread starting with one individual then onto the next through close contact by methods for hack/sniffing. The higher information on tuberculosis in this investigation as opposed to the examinations done at Namibia and Ethiopia could be because of the investigation populace that involved patients of medication safe tuberculosis a large portion of whom would have gotten past treatment and guided identifying with tuberculosis the board from their human services providers.

Practically all the members thought of it as significant the strategies that are fundamental for avoidance of contracting tuberculosis, spread and treatment of tuberculosis-like covering mouth while hacking or wheezing and legitimate removal of sputum. Be that as it may, about 4/5 of the patients announced after perilous removal of sputum. 33% of the patients were spitting in open and not keeping up a specific spot to dispose sputum.

CONCLUSION:

It was concluded during this study that despite of correct knowledge and attitude toward tuberculosis only a few ones are practically disposed of their sputum safely. There is a big gap in awareness about the correct disposal of sputum in people.

REFERENCES:

1. World Health Organization. Global Tuberculosis Report 2016. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2016.
2. Singla N, Singla R, Jain G, Habib L, Behera D. Tuberculosis among household contacts of multidrug-resistant tuberculosis patients in Delhi, India. *Int J Tuberc Lung Dis* 2011;15:1326-30.

3. Yang S, Lee GW, Chen CM, Wu CC, Yu KP. The size and concentration of droplets generated by coughing in human subjects. *J Aerosol Med* 2007;20:484-94.
4. World Health Organization. Tuberculosis. Blood Safety and Clinical Technology: Guideline on Standard Operating Procedures on Microbiology. Ch. 17. Geneva, Switzerland: World Health Organization; 2007.
5. Lala Ram Sarup Institute. Minutes of the 3rd Meeting of National Airborne Infection Control Committee, 2009. New Delhi, India: LRS Institute; 2009.
6. Ricks PM, Mavhunga F, Modi S, Indongo R, Zezai A, Lambert LA, *et al*. Characteristics of multidrug-resistant tuberculosis in Namibia. *BMC Infect Dis* 2012;12:385.
7. Revised National Tuberculosis Control Programme. National Strategic Plan for Tuberculosis Elimination 2017-2025. New Delhi, India: Central TUBERCULOSIS Division, Directorate General of Health Services. Government of India; 2017.
8. Esmael A, Ali I, Agonafir M, Desale A, Yaregal Z, Desta K. Assessment of patients' knowledge, attitude, and practice regarding pulmonary tuberculosis in Eastern Amhara regional state, Ethiopia: Cross-sectional study. *Am J Trop Med Hyg* 2013;88:785-8.
9. Bhatt G, Vyas S, Trivedil K. An epidemiological study of multi drug resistant tuberculosis cases registered under revised national tuberculosis control programme of Ahmedabad city. *Indian J Tuberc* 2012;59:18-27.
10. Bhattacharyya K, Rama R, Mitra SP, Bhattacharyya SK, Sarkar T, Dasgupta U, *et al*. Perceptions and practices of sputum-positive pulmonary tuberculosis patients regarding their disease and its management. *NTI Bull* 2005;41:11-7.
11. Rekha T, Singh P, Unnikrishnan B, Prasanna Mithra P, Kumar N, Prasad KD, *et al*. Sputum collection and disposal among pulmonary tuberculosis patients in coastal South